

The determinants of VET educators' occupational choice

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1. Introduction

Teachers' motivation is recognized as being of primary importance for the quality of education at any school level (OECD, 2005). It has consequences for a range of important outcomes, notably for the development of teachers' knowledge (König and Rothland, 2012), quality of teaching (Kunter *et al.*, 2008), students' outcomes (Butler, 2007), and students' motivation to learn (Pelletier *et al.*, 2002). Motivation to become a teacher has been a topic of interest for several decades; recently, however, its popularity in scientific research has quickly grown as researchers have become increasingly aware of its importance (Richardson and Watt, 2010). Most of the studies conducted so far concern primary/elementary teachers, general lower and upper secondary teachers and, less frequently, higher education or vocational education and training (VET) teachers. Whereas VET is believed to be central to the future of economic development across the world (Achtenhagen and Grubb, 2001; Grollmann, 2008; Guthrie *et al.*, 2009), there is a true paucity of scientific studies investigating the motivation of teachers and trainers at this level of education (for exceptions, see Nägele and Bestvater, 2012; Deschenaux and Roussel, 2008). Therefore, the present research aims to investigate individuals' motivation to become VET educators in Switzerland and to contrast these motivations with research on teachers at the primary and secondary general education levels.

A risk of teacher shortage exists in several countries, including Switzerland, due to several causes, such as an increase in recent decades in the percentage of VET teachers over the age of 50 years; this figure stood at 39% in 2009 (Swiss Federal Statistics Office, 2010). Studying the career choice of VET educators is a current and important question as the profession is not sufficiently esteemed (Grollmann, 2008) and this appreciation would be necessary in order to attract the most suitable individuals – those who will be the most committed and skilled teachers – to the profession (Guthrie *et al.*, 2009; OECD, 2005). In fact, the recent *Bruges Communiqué on Enhanced European*

Cooperation in VET for the Period 2011–2020 states that “The ageing European teacher and trainer population, changing labour markets and working environments, together with the need to attract those best suited to teaching make the objective of improving initial and continuing training of teachers even more critical.” (p. 8)

1.1. Studies on motivation to teach in Switzerland

Using sociopsychological frameworks, a few empirical studies investigated the reasons why individuals in Switzerland choose to become teachers at different schooling levels (Huberman, 1989/1993; Müller *et al.*, 2009; Nägele and Bestvater, 2012). Huberman (1989/1993) conducted interviews with 160 in-service teachers, 88 of whom were teaching in middle school and the other 72 in high school, in order to explore the life cycle of teachers. Among the topics investigated was their initial and later motivation to become teachers. Participants reported several motives, suggesting that they did not base their decision on a single reason but rather on a combination of reasons. The most important motivations for teaching, each of which was mentioned by at least one quarter of the teachers, were: contact with youth (32%), a way to earn a living (31%), love of the subject (29%), and discovery of a profession (25%). Twenty-two percent of the teachers also reported a “passive motivation,” stating that they chose teaching owing to the lack of a better option or by a process of elimination. Huberman found that middle school teachers showed a tendency to be more attracted by the social aspects of the profession in comparison to high school teachers, who favored the love of the discipline, lacked a better career option, and viewed it simply as a way to earn a living. This suggests that those teaching in high school, contrarily to the popular idea of teaching as a calling, did not choose the profession as a vocation.

Müller *et al.* (2009) conducted a survey of 306 primary and secondary pre-service teachers in Geneva. Four categories of motivation emerged as the most prominent: “humanistic values” (e.g., the wish to work with children and young people), “professional vocation” (e.g., identification with the teaching profession), “work conditions as characteristics of the profession” (e.g., possibility to work in a spirit of cooperation), and “extrinsic work conditions” (e.g., chance to reconcile private and professional life). With regard to the choice of a career in teaching, other types of motives – such as entering a profession with valuable social status, geographic mobility, or choice by default – were

generally less important. As with Huberman's study, there were differences found, that related to level of instruction: Pre-service teachers at the primary education level placed more emphasis on humanistic value and the psychological aspects of teaching, whereas those teaching adolescent students in secondary education reported being more attracted by working conditions such as schedule flexibility and holidays.

To our knowledge, only a single study explored the motivation to become a VET teacher in Switzerland: Nägele and Bestvater (2012), who investigated the degree of attractiveness of the teaching profession in Switzerland's vocational schools. One hundred and nineteen in-service instructors teaching vocational disciplines (health care and nursing, construction, electricity professions, and electronics) in Zürich were surveyed. The factors influencing the change from a profession in the field to the occupation of vocational teacher in the same field were found to be manifold. Self-efficacy for teaching[1], quality of memories of one's own schooling years, in addition to extrinsic motivations (such as improvement of working conditions in terms of flexibility and improvement of social status or income in the case of certain professions) were identified as the most central factors. Furthermore, circumstances, such as encouragement by others and experience as a substitute for another teacher, were reported by VET educators as also playing significant roles in these individuals' career choice. Two studies, one in Australia (Productivity Commission, 2010) and the other by Deschenaux and Roussel (2008) in Canada, corroborate this observation about the importance of circumstances in VET educators' career choice. In the Canadian study, it was found that of the sample of 152 VET teachers, as many individuals reported that becoming a teacher was not at all part of their initial career plan as those reporting that they had already thought about a career in teaching. This suggests that circumstances, such as being offered a teaching position by a professional school, could play a significant role in the choice to become a VET educator. We will refer to this as "opportunity choice."

1.2. Educators in vocational education and training

In Switzerland, individuals teaching vocational disciplines become educators as their second (and sometimes even lower on the scale) career, after several years working in their specialty areas. Of the various types of VET educators, two are of interest here: VET teachers teaching vocational

knowledge and VET trainers. The first teach in schools, where they provide instruction in vocational courses (in contrast to general knowledge or foreign language courses). These teachers were, or continue to be, professionals in the occupation that the apprentices are learning. They can, thus, be further divided into those for whom teaching is their main activity (that is, more than 50% of their time; hereafter designated as “full-time VET teachers”) and those for whom teaching is an auxiliary activity (that is, less than 50% of their time; hereafter named “part-time VET teachers”). The professional schools hire VET teachers who then undergo in-service teacher education, in most cases after a few years of teaching. Trainers, the second type of VET educators, work in industry training centers, trade schools, workshops, or laboratories. Like VET teachers, VET trainers are apprentices’ educators whose responsibility is to train future professionals in their fields by conveying professional knowledge and skills. They also undergo teacher education, in most cases after a few years of practice. The main distinction between the two types of VET educators is that VET teachers work in classrooms and teach theoretical knowledge (with limited possibilities to practically demonstrate the skills), whereas VET trainers teach their occupation in workshops or in enterprises and are oriented toward the practical aspects of the occupation. Note, however, that while both aim to support the apprentices in the development of “profession-specific knowledge,” in many recent curriculum reform models (e.g., competence-based educational programs), the division between “theoretical” and “practical” knowledge is intended to be overcome in order to facilitate students’ transfer of knowledge among the multiple places of learning (Akkerman and Bakker, 2012; Schaap *et al.*, 2012). Further important differences between both types of VET educators are found in their recruitment and working conditions. VET teachers follow the rhythm of a school year, including holidays like other teachers, school hours, homework correction, and test preparation and correction. They are employed by the state, which provides job security, and their salary is similar to other secondary education teachers’. In contrast, VET trainers have a private working contract, receive four or five weeks of holiday per year, work around 40 hours per week, have no job security, and follow company-specific rules. They have, in sum, the same working conditions as other professionals in their fields, the difference being the task to train apprentices. In terms of motivation to become a VET educator, the diversity of professional

roles, recruitment, and working conditions raise the issue of differences between the three types of VET educators.

In contrast to pre-service primary or secondary teachers generally questioned regarding their motivation to teach, some determinants may be more or less prominent for VET educators than for primary/secondary teachers. One may, for instance, wonder if the idea of a “vocation,” largely reported by primary education teachers (Müller *et al.*, 2009), is also present in VET educators. It is likely that VET educators resemble the secondary (high school) teachers interviewed by Huberman: They may primarily come to the profession for material (or work condition) reasons; some core activities of teaching, such as contact with young people, may be less important in their career choice; or they may have multiple motives, such as both material and social reasons.

A study of 90 second-career teachers, who left an occupation in the field of business, shed light on why these individuals made a choice that was believed to be very implausible (Richardson *et al.*, 2007). Using the Factors Influencing Teaching Choice (FIT-Choice) scale (described below), this study revealed that the determinants of the choice to become a teacher were largely similar to those observed in a larger cohort of pre-service teachers (Watt and Richardson, 2007), the majority of whom had no prior career. The most important motivations reported for choosing teaching were perceived ability to teach, personal and social utility values, and memories about their own learning experiences in teaching and learning (Richardson *et al.*, 2007). Social dissuasion was also quite strongly reported, meaning that these career changers’ relatives tried to discourage them from such a choice. In contrast, social encouragement and the consideration of teaching as a fallback career were rated as significantly less important motivations. Furthermore, analysis of how this group perceives teaching showed that, similar to the large cohort of pre-service teachers, this occupation was seen as high in demand but low in return. We interpret these last observations as meaning that teaching was not considered an easy occupation; individuals do not turn to teaching because it appears easy.

To sum up, given the dearth of important knowledge about VET educators’ motivation and the relevance of this information in regard to attracting the most engaged individuals, it is critical to focus on the reasons why individuals choose this occupation. The present study investigates this issue by analyzing the determinants of career choice among three types of VET educators and contrasting these

determinants to those classically emerging from studies on pre-service primary or secondary education teachers. A comprehensive framework of the determining factors of a career in teaching, like the one proposed by Watt and Richardson (2007), is required for this purpose.

1.3. The FIT-Choice framework and its adaptation

FIT-Choice, proposed by Watt and Richardson (2007, 2008; Richardson and Watt, 2006, 2010), is a framework for the study of motivation to teach. It is based on an expectancy-value theory of achievement motivation, originally addressing students' motivation for academic choices (Eccles, 2009; Eccles *et al.*, 1983). FIT-Choice arises from the observation that the field of teacher motivation suffers from a lack of theoretical foundations and valid instruments (Watt and Richardson, 2007). Thus, in keeping with expectancy-value theory, the framework proposes the organization of the most important reasons, based on study results, for becoming a teacher, as well as additional factors motivating this choice. These factors are mapped to the main constructs of the theory, permitting the incorporation of diverse motivations within an integrated and comprehensive motivational framework. Scales have been developed and validated for each model's component. A brief description of the framework's components is provided (see table 1) and a detailed explanation can be found in Watt and Richardson (2007) and Richardson and Watt (2010).

The first component is self-perceptions, which refers to perceived teaching ability. In the career choice literature, these perceptions are seen as fundamental since individuals choose occupations for which they think they have good abilities and contrarily, tend not to choose professions that do not fit their abilities (Hackett, 1995; Lent and Hackett, 1987).

Task value, the second component, is decomposed into three types (see Super and Bohn, 1970). *Intrinsic value* concerns the interest in the occupation. This is analogous to the construct of intrinsic motivation in other motivational frameworks, which can be described as a motivation that appears to “come from engagement in activities for their own sake, without any expectation of additional extrinsic incentives” (Lepper *et al.*, 2008). *Personal utility value* is represented by four constructs: “job security”, “job transferability”, “time for family”, and “bludging” (i.e. considering teaching as an undemanding occupation). We considered “job transferability”, i.e. perceptions of teaching as being useful for employment abroad and allowing for choice of where to live, as being

irrelevant to VET teachers and trainers in Switzerland, where it is culturally not valued to teach abroad; we consequently omitted this construct. Finally, *social utility value* is split into four constructs, namely “shape future of children/adolescents”, “enhance social equity”, “make social contribution”, and “work with children/adolescents”.

“Fallback career” refers to the choice of a career in teaching because the privileged (first) choice was not possible. This construct was not included in the research because teaching, by definition, represents a second career choice for VET educators. Thus, a construct called “opportunity” was developed to represent the choice of a career simply because the opportunity was offered. Quite frequently, VET educators come to the occupation by accident, without a well-developed intention to become a VET teacher or trainer (Bestvater and Nägele, 2010; Deschenaux and Roussel, 2008).

The third component refers to perceptions of the occupation, and is divided into *task demand* and *task return*. *Task demand* is subdivided into “expert career”, which represents the idea that teachers require a high level of expertise to perform their job, and “high demand”, signifying that the occupation is demanding both emotionally and in terms of workload. *Task return* is split into “social status”, “teacher morale”, and “salary”. The first represents the respect and status level of teachers in society, the second the feeling that teachers are valued by society, and the third the perception of teaching as a well-paid occupation.

The last component is antecedent socialization constructs. It is composed of *prior teaching and learning experiences* (how good were the individual’s prior experiences as a student and teacher?), *social influences* (to what extent has he/she been encouraged by significant others to go into teaching?), and *dissuasion* (to what extent has he/she been discouraged from going into teaching?).

Findings from studies using the FIT-Choice scale in various countries and contexts (Watt and Richardson, 2012; Watt *et al.*, 2012) revealed several similarities across studies. Notably, personal utility value is consistently reported as being of lower importance than social utility value; task demands are seen as high and task returns as somewhat lower.

Insert Table 1 about here.

1.4. Aim of the study and research questions

First, the present study aims to investigate the factors that play a role in the choice of a second career as a VET educator and to contrast these to the literature on pre-service primary/secondary education teachers' decision to become a teacher. These factors are conceptualized as motivations for and perceptions of the occupation. Thus, only the reasons for becoming an educator are analyzed; the reasons for leaving the former job are not considered. Second, the goal is to explore potential differences between types of VET educators. The following questions will drive the analyses and discussion of the results:

1. What are the most important determinants of VET educators' career choice?
2. How do these determinants differ between three types of VET educators (trainers, teachers for whom teaching is a main activity, and teachers for whom teaching is an auxiliary activity)?
3. What are the specificities of these determinants in VET educators in contrast to what the literature reveals on first-career teachers in primary and secondary education?

The first two questions will be addressed using the data of an empirical study we conducted, whereas the third question will be addressed, in the discussion section, by contrasting the literature on first career teachers in primary and secondary education with our data on VET educators.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

Six-hundred and five in-service VET educators participated in the study: 483 VET teachers and 122 VET trainers from the German- ($n = 412$; 68.1%) and French- ($n = 193$; 31.9%) speaking parts of Switzerland, two linguistically and culturally different regions. The sample consisted of all those who were undergoing training at the Swiss Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (SFIVET) during spring 2010 in order to graduate as VET educators. Among VET teachers, 253 were part-time teachers (less than 50% of their time) and 230 were full-time. The sample consisted of 396 males (65.5%) and 209 females (34.5%). The mean age was 40 years and 3 months

($SD = 7$ yrs. 5 months, ranging from 22 to 58 years). Teaching experience before beginning the training was 5 years and 3 months ($SD = 4$ yrs. 10 months, range from 6 months to 28 yrs.). The mean number of years working in an enterprise employing apprentices (i.e., working in an enterprise employing apprentices) before becoming a teacher or trainer was 6 years and 2 months ($SD = 7$ yrs. 4 months, ranging from 0 to 40 yrs.). Further information about education level and professional fields is reported in table 2.

Three subgroups of VET educators can be distinguished in our sample: part-time teachers, full-time teachers, and trainers. The part-time teacher teaches as an auxiliary activity (less than 50% of the time) and is usually still working sideline, generally in private business; for example, the hypothetical case of an electrician running his own business, in addition to teaching about basic electricity for six hours at a professional school. The second type of VET educator, the full-time teacher, teaches as his/her main professional activity; for example, the case of a cook who was working at a restaurant but has now changed his career to become a cooking teacher at a professional school. The last type of VET educator is the trainer who works at an industry training center, trade school, or workshop; for example, a watch-maker who was working for a private firm and decided to become a trainer in the training center of this same firm.

Table 2 shows the sociodemographic characteristics of the complete sample.

Insert Table 2 about here.

2.2. Procedure and instruments

As part of a larger anonymous survey, participants, divided into several groups, were asked, during a 45-minute class period, to provide information on several sociodemographic characteristics, their motivation to teach, and their perceptions of the occupation of VET educator. Definitions of the constructs assessed and sample items are provided in table 1.

2.2.1. Sociodemographic characteristics

Participants were asked to report their gender, year of birth, number of years of experience in teaching/training, number of years working in an enterprise employing apprentices before becoming a teacher/trainer, first profession learned, and the highest diploma obtained.

2.2.2. Factors influencing teaching choice: Motivation to teach and perceptions of teaching

The FIT-Choice model (Richardson and Watt, 2010; Watt and Richardson, 2007) was adapted according to the specificities of the VET Swiss system. As previously explained (1.3.), we removed one and added another construct from the original FIT-Choice framework according to cultural and contextual adaptations. In addition, because VET educators generally teach and train young people aged 16 to 20 years and above, the words “children and adolescents” were replaced by “young people” in the items and corresponding scale names. For the trainers, we modified the items slightly so that the words “teacher” and “teaching” were replaced respectively by “trainer” and “training.” We translated items from the FIT-Choice scales from the original English version to German and French.

The items assessing motivations to teach and perceptions of the occupation were respectively declarative and interrogative sentences from which participants had to choose an answer on a 7-point Likert scale. The anchors were respectively “1= not at all important” and “7 = extremely important” (for motivations) and “1 = not at all” and “7 = extremely” (for perceptions about VET).

After discussion of the translations with bilingual experts in education psychology and VET, the survey was pretested on a sample of 144 VET educators (former SFIVET students; 110 German speaking and 34 French speaking) to check the relevance of the items for this population and the quality of the translation. Results of this pilot study suggest that the scores of two scales, namely *intrinsic value* and *dissuasion*, were not sufficiently internally consistent (Cronbach's $\alpha < .60$) in the German language version. Therefore, we formulated an additional item in both languages. All other scales presented adequate properties in terms of internal consistency, response distribution, and intercorrelations. Furthermore, this pretest revealed that we targeted the most important determinants since no other reason for becoming VET teacher was repeatedly mentioned. The translated and adapted FIT-Choice scale has previously been validated by Berger & D'Ascoli (2012).

2.3. Analyses

As a preliminary step, we performed multiple group confirmatory factor analyses in order to check the validity of the items and scales. The goal was to investigate whether the French- and German-speaking translated items and scales have the same dimensionality as the original English-speaking version. Evidence of scales' metric invariance was found across the French and German languages and configural invariance was achieved with few differences (highlighted below) between the original English version and the translated versions. Akin to the original FIT-Choice scales (Watt and Richardson, 2007), the items "time for family" and "bludging" were found to load on one rather than two distinct factors and a single scale (namely *time for family*) was, consequently, formed. Additional merging was done between the scales "shape future of children/adolescents" and "make social contribution". Although the items composing these two scales were found to be distinct in Watt and Richardson's (2007) results, they loaded onto a single factor in our data (both in French and German languages). Among the four items developed to measure a choice by opportunity, one was removed ("some favorable circumstances brought me to teaching") because it did not load significantly on the expected factor, which was the case in both languages. Concerning perceptions of the occupation, and akin to the original FIT-Choice scales (Watt and Richardson, 2007), the items from the scales "social status" and "teacher morale" were found to load on a single factor and not on two independent factors. Consequently, the items were merged into a single scale (namely "social status"). We estimated internal consistency of scales' scores using Cronbach's α . For the French version, median α was .81 (ranging from $\alpha = .55$ for "high demand" to .87 for "work with youth"), and for the German version, median α was .84 (ranging from $\alpha = .72$ for "high demand" to .96 for "good salary"). Further information on these analyses can be found in Berger & D'Ascoli (2012).

The differences between the three types of VET professionals, namely part-time VET teachers, trainers, and full-time VET teachers, were then examined. The motivations to become a VET educator were the first to be explored, followed by perceptions of the occupation. A multivariate covariance analysis (MANCOVA) was performed, with type of VET educator as the independent variable (part-time teacher, full-time teacher, trainer), five dichotomous covariates (linguistic region, sex, age, parenthood, and education level ISCED 5A), and fifteen dependent variables (eleven

motivational dimensions and four dimensions representing perceptions of the occupation). We ran this analysis on 587 participants with complete answers, thus excluding 18 with incomplete responses.

3. Results

3.1. Factors influencing the choice to become VET educator at the sample level

Intrinsic value and perceived teaching ability appeared to be the two most important factors for all types of VET educators. The three components of social utility value were then rated over the mid-point of the scale. Prior teaching and learning experiences was rated sixth highest, just above opportunity. The two components of personal utility value were among the least important factors, both under the mid-point of the scale. Finally, social influences and dissuasion were reported to be the least important factors, with similar means suggesting that VET educators were slightly influenced in their career choice but also slightly dissuaded.

Regarding perceptions of the profession, the two indicators of task demand were rated as higher than the two indicators of task return. This suggests that what individuals perceive as a gain from becoming a VET educator is less than the difficulties they perceive in the profession.

3.2. Differences between types of VET educators: Motivations & perceptions of the occupation

With the use of Wilks' criterion, we found that the covariates were all significantly related to the fifteen combined DVs: linguistic region ($F_{15,565} = 6.885$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.16$), sex ($F_{15,565} = 5.207$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.12$), age ($F_{15,565} = 3.981$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.10$), parenthood ($F_{15,565} = 3.485$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.09$), and ISCED 5A education level ($F_{15,565} = 3.654$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.09$). Tests of within-subject effects revealed that each of the covariates provided adjustment to at least one of the DVs. After adjusting for differences on the covariates, the IV, type of VET educator still made a significant and non-negligible contribution to the DVs: ($F_{30,1130} = 3.796$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.09$).

Univariate ANCOVA (see table 3) showed that the IV had a significant effect on *intrinsic value*, “promote social equity”, “time for family”, and “job security”, meaning that different types of VET educators ascribe significantly different degrees of importance to these four factors in regard to their career choice.

Insert Table 3 about here.

Post-hoc using Tukey B's procedure revealed that VET teachers (both part-time and full-time) grant more importance than trainers to the promotion of social equity. Note that these groups do not differ in the other social utility value dimensions. Furthermore, the types of educators also differ in the two dimensions of *personal utility value*: Full-time VET teachers (teaching as their main professional activity) were more influenced than trainers by the prospect of having more time for family and by the security of the job. Part-time VET teachers (teaching as a minor professional activity) were less influenced by motivation for family time than their colleagues working full-time as teachers but more influenced than trainers. In terms of job security, part-time teachers and trainers did not differ.

Furthermore, univariate ANCOVA (see table 4.) showed that the IV had a significant effect on ratings of "good salary" and "high demand", but no effect on "social status" and "expert career". This indicates that different types of VET educators hold significantly different specific perceptions of their profession.

Insert Table 4 about here.

Post-hoc using Tukey B's procedure revealed that, in terms of *task return*, whereas full-time VET teachers believe that teaching is a job with better wage conditions than trainers do, the latter and part-time VET teachers perceive the social status of their occupation in a manner that is similar to the perception of VET teachers. *Task demand* also differs among the types of educators: Full-time teachers believe that their job is more demanding in terms of emotion and workload than part-time teachers do (trainers are in-between and do not significantly differ from the two other groups). Full-time teachers, however, perceive their job as requiring the same level of expertise as both part-time teachers and trainers.

4. Discussion and implications

The aims of this study were to investigate the relative importance of factors influencing the choice of a career as a VET educator, and the differences between three types of VET educators with regard to these factors.

Our results are strikingly similar to those of other studies using the FIT-Choice scale (Watt and Richardson, 2012) and to Richardson *et al.*'s (2007) study concerning second-career teachers formerly employed in the field of business. In general, teachers' motivations are very similar across contexts. In terms of motivation, intrinsic value is the most important determinant of a career as a VET teacher. Interpreted together with the high rating of social utility value dimensions and the low rating of personal utility value dimensions, we conclude that VET educators value the activity of teaching more than the potential advantages it may offer, as conceptualized in the personal utility construct. Furthermore, we interpret the high rating of perceived teaching ability as reflecting the fact that feeling competent in teaching plays the role of a pre-condition for those who choose to become VET educators; this is congruent with career choice literature (Eccles, 2009; Eccles *et al.*, 1983; Lent and Hackett, 1987). This feeling of self-efficacy probably reflects educators' high perceived degree of content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge needed for quality teaching. This adds to the argument of a valuable general profile of career choice determinants for VET educators. Analysis of the role of antecedent socialization constructs reveals that prior teaching and learning experiences is the only dimension coming into play in this career choice. Thus, it seems that good memories about one's own schooling constitute not only a reason to become a primary or secondary education teacher as a first career, but also a reason to become a second-career VET teacher or trainer. Even though becoming a VET educator was not part of the initial career plan and, therefore, could not be described as a vocation – as it is, for instance, for many primary education teachers – it might be seen as a condition in the choice to turn to teaching when this becomes an alternative. In contrast, both encouragement and dissuasion from surrounding influences play a minor role. This is in contrast to the observations of some studies (Richardson *et al.*, 2007) and may depend on the original field from which the second-career teacher originates. For instance, in Richardson *et al.*'s study, changing from business to teaching is perceived as an implausible move and thus social dissuasion – though rated

around the mid-point of the scale and thus moderate – is exerted on this choice. In the present study, no significant relationship between professional field and dissuasion was, however, observed. The minor importance of social influences observed in VET educators could also be related to the teachers' or future teachers' age: in regard to career decisions, relatives probably have a greater influence on young pre-service teachers than on adults in their 30s or 40s. The new dimension we introduced in the framework, "opportunity," was rated as being in the middle of the motivations. This confirms the significant role of the offered opportunity in regard to becoming a VET educator. Furthermore, this result corroborates observations by others (Bestvater and Nägele, 2010; Deschenaux and Roussel, 2008) about the significant role of circumstances in such a choice and reflects the fact that the profession of VET educator is somewhat hidden.

Regarding VET educators' perceptions of teaching, we found that task return is rated as lower than task demand. This holds for both dimensions of perception. Again, this was also observed by Richardson *et al.* (2007) with regard to teachers formerly working in business, as well as in most studies worldwide that used the FIT-Choice framework (Watt and Richardson, 2012). Our interpretation is that social status and level of salary[2], the latter being particularly high in Switzerland (OECD, 2011), are not seen as strong determinants of VET educators' career choice. Furthermore, teaching is seen as a challenging occupation, suggesting that VET educators did not choose it because it appeared easy to them.

The results of the present study show that some determinants of career choice differ between types of educators, even after controlling for the effects of linguistic region, sex, age, parenthood, and education level. Thus, we are confident in the robustness of the results. Regarding the motivations, our results showed that significant differences were still found in the case of three reasons for becoming VET educators, all related to task value: promotion of social equity, time for family, and job security. Full-time VET teachers ascribe more importance than other VET educators to both personal utility value constructs. Not surprisingly, regarding job security, the results reveal that this factor is more important for those who decided to become full time teachers than it is for part-time teachers and trainers. Time for family is unsurprisingly higher for part-time VET teachers (and full-time VET teachers) than for trainers, meaning that flexible working conditions (in terms of work-life balance)

play a more important role for both types of teachers than for trainers; this is understandable as the former enjoy more flexibility in managing their working time than the latter whose working time is set by the firm. Promotion of social equity was found to be more important for teachers than trainers, suggesting that, contrary to the other social utility value constructs (work with young people and make social contribution), this aspect of social utility value drives teachers in their career choice.

Interesting results were found regarding perceptions of the VET educator profession. Two types of perceptions, namely “good salary” and “high demand”, significantly differed between types of educators, indicating differing perceptions of the occupation. Both types of VET teachers rated their perception of salary as more favorable than trainers did. However, full-time VET teachers see the social status of their occupation as lower (though the difference does not reach statistical significance) than the others. Thus, those working full-time in professional schools see more *task return* in terms of salary but less return in terms of professional prestige. *Task demand* was rated as more important in terms of high demand by full-time compared to part-time teachers but, at the same time, full-time teachers perceived the job as requiring less expertise than other educators did.

In conclusion, VET educators’ determinants of career choice partly correspond to the results of research on other populations of teachers. Teaching is not perceived as an easy task and individuals choose it as a profession fitting their values and aptitudes. Nevertheless, choice by opportunity plays an important role, which seems to be specific to VET teachers as this aspect is generally not revealed in the study of first-career teachers. Our study shows that there are partly different determinants among types of VET educators; personal utility value dimensions, in particular, play a more important role for full-time VET teachers, suggesting that individuals valuing these dimensions would choose to become teachers as their main activity rather than as an auxiliary activity.

The results should be interpreted within several limits of this study. First, we did not directly investigate the reasons for leaving the former occupation. Thus, only one face of the coin, attraction toward teaching, was explored (see Berger & D’Ascoli, 2012 for such an analysis of VET teachers). The reasons for quitting may provide a more detailed and comprehensive picture of VET educators’ career choice, which further research should consequently include. Second, the data were self-reported and this was done several years after the choice was effectively made. Although the survey was

anonymous, social desirability may have influenced participants' answers, most probably in their report about the importance of personal utility value factors since it might be difficult to confess that one has chosen a career based on human relationships for its expected material advantages. Furthermore, some distortion in the answers may appear due to the delay between the choice and the moment our survey was conducted. However, longitudinal research using the FIT-Choice scale showed that, among a sample of Australian teachers, motivations do not fluctuate much over a five-year period (Richardson and Watt, 2010). Finally, we acknowledge the potential role of unconscious motivation, such as the desire for a corrective emotional experience, in the choice to become a teacher (Riley, 2009). Uncovering this type of motivation would, however, require a different methodological and theoretical framework.

The implications of the results are that attractiveness of the profession of VET educator can be increased and promoted by noticeably displaying the social utility value and the challenges of the profession in terms of task demand. For full-time teachers, personal utility value (time for family and job security) can also be promoted as a reason to turn to the profession. In addition to investigating the reasons for leaving the former profession, we believe that future research should investigate the implications of motivation to teach for teachers' professional development. We conjecture that, depending on their motivation, VET educators may develop pedagogical knowledge, beliefs, and practices in different directions, which would surely affect VET students' learning. It is, therefore, important for future research to look at the factors predicting the quality of teaching, including motivation to become a teacher.

In these times of teacher shortage threat, the present study brings important information about the factors that might attract new VET educators. These factors can be used to promote the occupation and raise the attention of professionals on the valuable aspects of teaching in VET. Furthermore, this study is, to the best of our knowledge, the first to look at the determinants of VET educators career choice using an expectancy-value framework (in this case the FIT-Choice framework; Watt and Richardson, 2007) and comparing different types of VET educators for the importance of multiple factors in their career choice. It constitutes an initial effort in understanding the psychology of this

population of educators and will be followed by studies investigating how VET teachers and trainers teach in the specific context of VET and how they learn and develop during their career.

Notes

1. “Teacher efficacy [or self-efficacy for teaching] is the teacher’s belief in her and his ability to organize and execute the courses of action required to successfully accomplish a specific teaching task in a particular context” (Tschannen-Moran, Woolfolk Hoy, and Hoy, 1998).

2. Based partly on the same sample (with the exception of the trainers) as the present study, Hof, Strupler, and Wolter (2011) investigated the importance of wage factors as a determinant of career choice. They found that monetary factors were not decisive in Swiss VET teachers’ career choice. This is in line with our results.

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Table 1.

Description of the constructs from the modified FIT-choice framework

Construct	Definition	Sample item	# items
<i>*Opportunity</i>	Choosing teaching simply by opportunity	The opportunity to teach was available	4
PERCEPTION OF THE OCCUPATION			
<i>Perceived teaching ability</i>	Choosing teaching as a career fitting one's abilities	I have the qualities of a good teacher.	3
TASK VALUE			
<i>Intrinsic value</i>	Choosing teaching for intrinsic motives like interest	I like teaching.	4
<i>Social utility value</i>			
Shape future of young people	Choosing teaching to influence young people's values	Teaching will allow me to influence the next generation.	2
Enhance social equity	Choosing teaching to help the socially disadvantaged and raise their ambitions	Teaching will allow me to raise the ambitions of under-privileged youth.	2
Make social contribution	Choosing teaching to offer a service to the society and contribute to it	Teaching will allow me to provide a service to society.	3
Work with young people	Choosing teaching to work and help young people	I want a job that involves working with young people.	4
<i>Personal utility value</i>			
Job security	Choosing teaching to get a secure job in terms of reliable income and solid path career	Teaching will provide a secure job.	3
Time for family	Choosing teaching to get more time for one's family life and commitments (quality of life)	Teaching hours will fit with the responsibilities of having a family.	3
Bludging	Choosing teaching as an easy option since working day seems to be short and holidays long	As a teacher I will have lengthy holidays	2
ANTECEDENT SOCIALIZATION CONSTRUCTS			
<i>Prior teaching and learning experiences</i>	Perception of the quality of past experiences as a learner or in a teaching role	I have had inspirational teachers.	3
<i>Social influences</i>	Perception of the extent to which one has been encouraged or persuaded to go into teaching	My colleagues thought I should become a teacher	3
<i>Dissuasion</i>	Perception of the extent to which one has been dissuaded to go into teaching	Did others tell you teaching was not a good career choice?	3

PERCEPTIONS OF THE OCCUPATION			
<i>Task demand</i>			
High demand	Perception of teaching as being demanding emotionally and in terms of work load	Do you think teachers have a heavy workload	3
Expert career	Perception of teaching as requiring high levels of specialized knowledge	Do you think teaching requires high levels of expert knowledge?	2
<i>Task return</i>			
Good salary	Perception of teaching as a well-paid occupation	Do you think teaching is well paid?	2
Social status	Perception of teaching as socially respected and a high status career	Do you believe teachers are perceived as professionals?	3
Teacher morale	Perception of teachers' morale and feeling socially valued	Do you think teachers feel valued by society?	3

Note. * Additional factor developed.

Table 2.

Sample description (n = 605)

Variable	n	%
<i>Type of VET educator</i>		
Teacher as auxiliary activity (“part-time teacher”)	253	41.8
Teacher as main activity (“full-time teacher”)	230	38.0
Trainer	122	20.2
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	396	65.5
Female	209	34.5
<i>Linguistic region</i>		
German speaking	412	68.1
French speaking	193	31.9
<i>Education level</i>		
ISCED3A (General upper secondary education)	48	7.9
ISCED3B (Vocational upper secondary education)	10	1.7
ISCED5A (First stage of general tertiary education)	142	23.5
ISCED5B (First stage of vocational tertiary education)	396	65.5
ISCED6 (Second stage of tertiary education)	8	1.3
Missing information	1	0.2
<i>Professional field</i>		
Farming, forest economy, and breeding	14	2.3
Industry, craft industry	178	29.4
Technics and informatics	89	14.7
Building and mining	46	7.6
Commerce, transportation, and traffic	27	4.5
Hotel business, catering, and personal service	57	9.4
Management, administration, banking, insurance, and law	46	7.6
Health, teaching, culture, and science	141	23.3
Missing information	7	1.2

Note: ISCED = International Standard Classification of Education; Professional field categorized

according to Swiss Federal Statistics Office

Table 3.

Motivations to choose the career in the three groups

Construct	Part-time VET teachers (n = 245)		Full-time VET teachers (n = 221)		VET trainers (n = 121)		Total (n = 587)		F	p	Partial η^2
	M	(SD)	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Intrinsic value	5.87	(0.93)	6.02	(0.86)	6.09	(0.72)	5.97	(0.87)	2.601	0.075	-
Perceived teaching ability	5.34	(1.00)	5.56	(0.95)	5.46	(0.79)	5.45	(0.94)	3.070	0.047	0.01
Opportunity	4.38	(1.18)	4.38	(1.23)	4.40	(1.19)	4.38	(1.20)	0.596	0.552	-
<i>Social utility value</i>											
Promote social equity	4.51 _b	(1.51)	4.52 _b	(1.46)	4.13 _a	(1.53)	4.44	(1.50)	3.588	0.028	0.01
Work with young people	5.16	(1.29)	5.39	(1.20)	5.26	(1.13)	5.27	(1.23)	1.559	0.211	-
Make social contribution	5.18	(1.10)	5.17	(1.06)	5.18	(1.06)	5.18	(1.08)	0.264	0.768	-
<i>Personal utility value</i>											
Time for family	2.94 _b	(1.43)	3.42 _c	(1.47)	2.50 _a	(1.18)	3.03	(1.44)	14.469	< 0.001	0.05
Job security	3.70 _a	(1.45)	4.22 _b	(1.50)	3.69 _a	(1.53)	3.89	(1.51)	8.428	0.001	0.03
<i>Antecedent socialization</i>											
Prior teaching and learning experiences	4.21	(1.56)	4.57	(1.53)	4.50	(1.59)	4.41	(1.56)	1.554	0.212	-
Social influences	2.49	(1.53)	2.83	(1.67)	2.51	(1.52)	2.63	(1.59)	0.292	0.747	-
Dissuasion	2.40	(1.33)	2.66	(1.52)	2.19	(1.32)	2.46	(1.41)	1.831	0.161	-

Note: The F, p-value, and partial eta-squared are results from global one-way ANCOVA. Means within a row with another subscript are statistically significantly different (Tukey-B post-hoc test).

Table 4.

Perceptions of the profession in the three groups

Constructs	Part-time VET teachers (n = 245)		Full-time VET teachers (n = 221)		VET trainers (n = 121)		Total (n = 587)		F	P	Partial η^2
	M	(SD)	M	(SD)	M	(SD)	M	(SD)			
<i>Task return</i>											
Good salary	4.84 _b	(1.40)	4.57 _b	(1.34)	4.02 _a	(1.57)	4.57	(1.45)	13.217	< 0.001	0.04
Social status	4.43	(1.01)	4.17	(1.03)	4.47	(1.03)	4.34	(1.03)	2.389	0.093	-
<i>Task demand</i>											
High demand	5.41 _a	(0.99)	5.67 _b	(0.90)	5.50 _{a,b}	(0.90)	5.53	(0.94)	3.508	0.031	0.01
Expert career	5.98	(0.92)	5.74	(0.90)	5.95	(0.84)	5.88	(0.90)	0.519	0.595	-

Note: The F, p-value, and partial eta-squared are results from global one-way ANCOVA. Means within a row with another subscript are statistically significantly different (Tukey-B post-hoc test).

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